

FOREIGN INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE

TRENDS OF SCIENCE DEVELOPMENT AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES

October 16, 2022
SPECIAL ISSUE

THEMED
COLLECTION
OF PAPERS

Nicaragua, Managua

Colección temática de artículos de la Conferencia Científica Internacional Extranjera «Tendencias en el desarrollo de la ciencia y desafíos globales» por INIH «Desarrollo nacional» en cooperación con AFP. Octubre de 2022. – Managua (Nicaragua): INIH «Desarrollo nacional», AFP, 2022. – 60 p. URL: <https://disk.yandex.ru/d/9tRZWauErutwDQ> (fecha de publicación: 16.10.2022)

Themed collection of papers from Foreign International Scientific Conference «Trends in the development of science and Global challenges» by HNRI «National development» in cooperation with AFP. October 2022. – Managua (Nicaragua): HNRI «National development», AFP, 2022. – 60 p. URL: <https://disk.yandex.ru/d/9tRZWauErutwDQ> (publication date: 16.10.2022)

DOI 10.37539/MAN4.2022.11.13.001

ISBN 978-5-00213-026-9

Los materiales de la conferencia se publican en la colección **Foreign International Scientific Conference «Trends in the development of science and Global challenges»** (Conferencia científica internacional extranjera «Tendencias en el desarrollo de la ciencia y desafíos globales») Instituto Estatal de Investigaciones «Desarrollo Nacional», celebrada en Octubre de 2022:

La colección incluye artículos seleccionados recomendados para su publicación por el Consejo Editorial y Editorial del Instituto Nacional de Investigaciones para el Desarrollo.

La publicación está dirigida a trabajadores científicos y pedagógicos de organizaciones científicas e industriales, instituciones educativas.

Publicación científica

*La colección se publica sin cambios editoriales.
La responsabilidad del contenido de los artículos recae en los autores.*

**MATERIALES DE LA CONFERENCIA CIENTÍFICA INTERNACIONAL EXTRANJERA
«TENDENCIAS EN EL DESARROLLO CIENTÍFICO Y DESAFÍOS MUNDIALES»**

**MATERIALS OF THE FOREIGN INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
«TRENDS IN SCIENCE DEVELOPMENT AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES»**

OCTUBRE 2022

Managua, Nicaragua

Colección de artículos seleccionados

ISBN 978-5-00213-026-9

Managing editor Y.F. Elsesser
Responsible for the release of L.A. Pavlov, E.Garcia
Signed for printing from the original layout 16/10/2022.
Format 60x84/8. Digital printing Typeface
Times New Roman. Conditional printed sheets 3,6.
Volume - 10 Mb. Order No. 42302.
From Humanitarian National Research Institute
«National Development»

ISBN 978-5-00213-026-9

© HNRI «National development», 2022

© Autofast Publisher, 2022

© Group of authors, 2022

**TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF SCIENCE AND GLOBAL CHALLENGES**

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

MAGNETÓMETROS BASADOS EN SENSORES DE CUARZO MAGNETOMETERS BASED ON QUARTZ SENSORS

Anotación: El documento muestra la historia del desarrollo de la instrumentación magnetométrica de cuarzo en IZMIRAN desde la creación de dispositivos analógicos hasta los digitales modernos.

IZMIRAN es la única organización en Rusia que desarrolla y fabrica equipos de alta precisión basados en sensores magnéticos de cuarzo para el registro y estudio de variaciones geomagnéticas. Todos los observatorios magnéticos y muchos puntos de observación en Rusia, así como los observatorios extranjeros, están equipados con este equipo.

Abstract: The paper shows the history of the development of quartz magnetometric instrumentation at IZMIRAN from the creation of analog to modern digital devices.

IZMIRAN is the only organization in Russia that develops and manufactures high-precision equipment based on quartz magnetic sensors for the registration and study of geomagnetic variations. All magnetic observatories and many observation points in Russia, as well as foreign observatories, are equipped with this equipment.

Palabras clave: Campo magnético, sensores de cuarzo, estaciones de variación magnética, magnetómetros de cuarzo, observatorios magnéticos, datos digitales.

Keywords: Magnetic field, quartz sensors, magnetic variation stations, quartz magnetometers, magnetic observatories, digital data.

INTRODUCTION

IZMIRAN is currently the only organization in Russia that develops and manufactures high-precision equipment based on quartz magnetic sensors (**QMS**) for the registration and study of geomagnetic variations. All magnetic observatories (**MO**) and many observation points (**OP**) in Russia, as well as foreign observatories, are equipped with this equipment.

This review does not aim to show the entire history of the development of quartz magnetometric instrumentation in IZMIRAN from the day of its foundation (in the late forties – early fifties of the last century) to the present day – from the creation of analog to modern digital devices. Only the moments that are related to the introduction of digital technologies in quartz magnetometric instrumentation over the past 40 years are reflected in detail, and, at the same time, the process of development of quartz instrumentation in IZMIRAN is shown. Options for the creation, description and comparative analysis of digital magnetovariation stations (**DMVS**) of a new generation based on QMS are also given.

The review contains a large number of fundamental publications of the Institute's employees, as well as some of their publications of recent years in this area of activity [1-43]. Information is also provided on DMVS, which (on the basis of QMSs developed at IZMIRAN) were created by other organizations in the period of the 70s... 90s of the last century in the community and with the participation of the staff of the institute [9, 11-13, 15, 16, 39].

A BIT OF HISTORY

The first publications of the Institute's employees on devices based on QMS date back to 1949, when V.F. Schelting developed the design of a universal torsional quartz frame. Subsequently (on the basis of this development), he created a prototype Z-magnetometer for work in the field [1], as well as a field magnetic variation station (**MVS**) [2]. In 1954, a young researcher V.N. Bobrov joined these works. Together with V.F. Schelting, in 1956 they received an author's certificate [3] for the use of a quartz twisting frame in magnetometric devices [see Fig. 1]. Given the great

prospects of these works, during this period of time a creative group of employees for the development of quartz magnetometers was created at the institute. Judging by all known publications, the process of creating quartz magnetometric equipment in IZMIRAN can be divided into several specific stages:

1. Development of the theory of quartz magnetic variational devices and creation of the first samples of quartz sensors of various designs (1948-1960);
2. Development of the theory of quartz static magnetometers and ways to expand their technical capabilities. Start of mass production of quartz sensors for various applications. Beginning of creation and introduction of quartz analog stations of various designs (1961-1974);
3. Development of sensors with electrical output and conversion of analog signal into digital code. Beginning of the first samples digital stations development of various designs. Serial production of some samples of DMVS and their use in the MO, on the OP and in expeditionary conditions (1975-1999);
4. Creation of a new generation of DMVS on the basis of modern technologies and methods of storage, transmission and collection of data received. Application of DMVS in various conditions and on various MO and OP. Creation of a network of digital MOs and databases (2000 – present).

Figure 1 – The founders of quartz magnetic instrumentation are IZMIRAN and one of the first patents

Until the sixties of the last century, variational devices of foreign production were used to register variations in the Earth's magnetic field (**EMF**) on the MO of our country. To do this, magnetic scales and Z-variometers were used, which are a permanent magnet with a mirror suspended on one or two quartz threads. The accuracy of these instruments was very low due to the influence of temperature, humidity and other factors on them [4, 39]. In the period from 1954 to 1957, S.M. Mansurov [see Fig. 1] conducted practical research on the creation of an experimental

sample of the Z-variometer for the MO, as a result of which he published a work on the theory of magnetic variational devices [4]. This theory was then successfully developed by Yu.A. Burtsev in his dissertation work for quartz magnetometers [10] in 1970.

In 1962, the journal "Geomagnetism and Aeronomy" published an article by V.N. Bobrov entitled "A series of quartz magnetic variometers" [7], which opened a new direction in magnetic instrumentation. As a result, to register variations in the components of the magnetic induction vector (**MIV**) of the Earth's field in the MO, quartz variometers of the V. N. Bobrov system [5-9, 11] began to be used everywhere, displacing obsolete foreign analogues from observations (see Fig.2).

Quartz variometer of the Bobrov systems

MVS IZMIRAN-4

Figure 2 – Quartz variometers of the V. N. Bobrov system and MVS IZMIRAN-4

Many creative ideas of V.N. Bobrov were embodied in real devices solely thanks to the art of the quartz master N.D. Kulikov (see Fig. 3). The magnetometer schemes of the "Bobrov system" and QMS were protected by many copyright certificates and patents [3, 39]. In total, in the period from 1956 to 1990, V.N. Bobrov and colleagues-co-authors patented 62 new ideas-solutions for the design of quartz devices. Which at that time (from 1964 to 1975) was part of the Institute of the SKB IZMIRAN, and then the SKB FP AS USSR, produced QMS and devices designed by V.N. Bobrov by the dozens and hundreds [7-9, 11, 13]. Thus, one of the most successful designs of the MVS, developed in the SKB IZMIRAN, was the field magnetovariation station "IZMIRAN-4" [9, 13]. This development of the MVS turned out to be so successful that it was produced for many years serially and was used both in many domestic and foreign MO, and in scientific research and, especially, for expeditionary and field work (see Fig.2).

Figure 3 – Founders, creators of quartz magnetic instrumentation in IZMIRAN Bobrov V.N. and their students and followers

FROM ANALOG QUARTZ DEVICES TO DIGITAL

The first known publications of the Institute's employees related to the creation of DMVS and experimental work with them date back to 1975 – 1977. At this time, prototypes of QMS with an electrical output based on various designs of homemade or industrial photoelectric converters (PEC) appeared [39]. In the period from 1977 to 1979, some creative teams and researchers proposed methods and various options for converters of the analog signal QMS (with the output of the PEC) into a digital code. These proposals of theirs later served as the beginning of the development and manufacture of various designs of converters [39] voltage / code or current / code (at that time there were no microcircuits of modern ADCs).

One of these creative groups of employees of the Institute under the leadership of A.N. Zaitsev supervised for several years the development and manufacture of the first versions of the DMVS, which was conducted by the SKB FP. On the part of the SKB FP, the group of designers was led by V.I. Odintsov and this group was based on QMS prototypes of digital stations DMVS-1 and DMVS-2 [15, 39], some of which were then installed on various MO for testing [17, 39]. It should be noted that V.I. Odintsov, working with a group of associates in the SKB FP in the period from 1975 to 2017, made a great creative contribution to the quartz magnetic instrumentation of the Institute. With his direct participation, SKB FP created several models of DMVS [16, 39] for various applications and he was also engaged in conducting full-scale tests of DMVS in various conditions and environments [19, 39]. Some design new solutions for the created devices were patented and copyright certificates were obtained [39].

At the same time, creative groups of employees under the leadership of B.A. Belov and Yu.A. Burtsev, as well as groups of employees under the leadership of V.N. Bobrov, V.O. Papitashvili and S.P. Gaidash were active. These teams of employees developed directions in the creation of both field and observation devices [39] and devices for conducting research in marine conditions [14, 39]. Design solutions of the created prototypes of devices were repeatedly patented [39].

Thus, under the leadership of V.O. Papitashvili, an observational version of the DMVS called "DIMARS" was developed (on the basis of the QMS designed by V.N. Bobrov), which made it possible to register the received digital data on a flexible magnetic disk. In 1988, together with the engineers of the Budapest University of Eötvös, a small batch of 3 such devices was manufactured, which were installed and successfully used by magnetologists in the MO of Hungary and India. The main technical characteristics of the DMVS "DIMARS" can be found in the Table in the work [38].

Work on the creation of a bottom magnetovariation station by S.P. Gaidash and A.G. Goydina was started in early 1978. And within a year, the first prototype of the quartz bottom MVS (DMVS) was made for marine research. The first publications on this work date back to 1979 [14, 39]. The complexity and uniqueness of this work was that it was necessary to orient the sensitive element of the station in a certain way in the aquatic environment – at the bottom of the sea. The solution to this problem was achieved by the authors by fastening the QMS in a gimbal. At the same time, to orient the sensors along the magnetic meridian, a model of the so-called "unfolding transformation" scheme was used, which was patented by the authors of the development [39]. A group of IZMIRAN employees made several models of DMVS, and the authors of the developments took a direct part in their full-scale tests in various waters of the seas. The results of these studies are given by S.P. Gaidash in his dissertation [25].

It should be noted that all design solutions and schemes of the DMBC were made using (at that time) the most modern element base and technologies, using programmable elements and blocks that allow flexible rebuilding the metrological properties of the system. The best values in the world practice of such important characteristics as long-term stability of metrological parameters and low power consumption have been achieved. The main design solutions and ideas of this creative group of employees are protected by nine copyright certificates for inventions [39].

In 1977, IZMIRAN began joint work with the SKB FP to create a prototype of an automatic MVS (AMVS) designed to work in the conditions of Antarctica [12]. These works were carried out under the scientific guidance of the famous polar explorer S.M. Mansurov. The main requirements for the AMVS were as follows- the station should be made as a "measuring platform" (**MP**), which would include the possibility of recording in analog form (on photographic film) not only variations of the MIV components of the Earth's field, but also the possibility of registering changes in the leveling (orientation in space) of the station and QMS in two planes. And also this MP must record the temperature inside the magnetometric measuring converter (**MMC**) and the external environment.

Several samples of quartz AMVS were created, which were then installed by IZMIRAN staff on the OP in Antarctica [17], where they worked for 15 years while providing a scientific experiment called "Geophysical Polygon in Antarctica".

At the beginning of 1980, according to the terms of reference of IZMIRAN, the next stage of work was started in the SKB FP AS USSR to create an experimental series of digital AMVS for Antarctica. This project was called the AMVS "Penguin" [38]. The development of the station design was made using the first domestic large hybrid chips K-MOP technology, the characteristics of which ensured the operation of all station circuits on the OP in the harsh conditions of sub-zero temperatures of the Antarctic. As a result, the SKB FP produced a pilot batch of these devices, which were installed on the OP in Antarctica. In total, from 5 (in 1975) to 12 (in 1989) simultaneously operating AMVS took part in experiments and scientific research [17, 39].

In the period from 1985 to 1990, these works were continued – the designers of the SKB FP developed a DMVS for Antarctica under the name DMVS-6 [16] and released a pilot batch of 3 devices.

In the early 80s, according to the technical task of IZMIRAN, the SKB FP AS USSR carried out a serial production of 53 DMVS on the basis of QMS called DMVS-2 [15], which, with the active participation of the institute's employees [17, 19, 38], were then installed on the network of the MO of the USSR, including on the OP in the Far North (FN) (see Fig. 4). During this period of time, a team of IZMIRAN researchers together with employees of the Department of Geophysics of the Arctic and Antarctic Research Institute (AARI) supervised work related to ensuring the operability of the DMVS on the OP, conducted expeditionary and research work at observation points at the FN [34]. Since 1985, some of the DMVS-2 stations installed in the area of the FN have long been conducting a digital registration of data, as a result of which a database of digital 1-minute data of the MO and the OP (located in the area of the FN) was created and published, which were included in the database of digital data of the MO of Russia for the period 1984-2000. [19].

Figure 4 – Schemes of installed DMVS at magnetic observatories and observation points in Russia and abroad

Currently, on some MO, these instruments are in working condition, for example, in the observatory "Cape Schmidt" and the OP "Cape Kamenny" [38]. But in most observatories DMVS-2 is no longer used, since this device has a rather large physical size and energy consumption, and the electronics are outdated and do not have a direct connection with a modern computer.

The first works of the creative group of employees under the leadership of B.A. Belov and Yu.A. Burtsev date back to the beginning of 1977, when their joint publication [39] on work on digital converters for QMS was published. Then (from 1977 to 1981) a number of works related to the study of the stability of QMS, PEC, followed, and several copyright certificates were obtained to improve the optical system of QMS and PEC (1983) and international patents (1984) for the implementation of DMVS on their basis [39].

Figure 5 – General view of the equipment that is part of the DMVS "Quartz-3EM" and one of the device creators Yu.A. Burtsev

In the period from 1990 to 1993, this team of employees created a new model of DMVS called "Quartz-3" [18, 20]. This new model of DMVS (see Fig. 5) was superior to the DMVS-2 in many basic technical characteristics and differed from other models of DMVS (see table in the work [38]), created at that time at the Institute, patented by the authors of the original design of the PEC in QMS [39].

One of the first copies of the DMVS Quartz-3E was installed at the Australian Antarctic Observatory Davis in 1992 [18]. In 1994, the Quartz-3E model was manufactured for the University of Michigan in the USA and installed by IZMIRAN staff in Antarctica (at the Vostok station). Data from this DMBC via a U.S. communications satellite have been transmitted to the U.S. IDC in real time for 5 years (since 1995). A similar experiment on data transmission through the Japanese satellite IZMIRAN was carried out in 1998. The data came from the Quartz-3E DMVS, which was installed at the Tiksi Geophysical Observatory (IKIR DVSC), with the help of MP, which was created by employees of the Japanese University in Kyoto. As a result, the Quartz-3 series (its various models with a total of 30 devices) have found their application in scientific programs and research both in Russia and abroad. For example, at the FN (in the aurora zone), the Quartz-3E series DMVS are installed (see Fig. 4) from the OP of Cape Uelen in the east to the Sodankylä MO (Finland) [18, 34, 40]. The total number of stations installed at the FN is 12.

DMVS "Quartz-3" is successfully used at the present time in international programs, including INTERMAGNET (at the MO "Irkutsk", "Beijing", "Sodanklya", "Tihan").

At the beginning of the 21st century, the process of creating new magnetometric instruments at IZMIRAN was revived. Of the remaining leading specialists in the field of magnetic instrumentation, the Scientific and Production Laboratory of Geomagnetic Instruments and Measurements (SPL) was established in November 2004. It was necessary to restore the previously

lost pace in the creation of new modern MMCs and magnetometers based on modern technologies, on the basis of various types of magnetosensitive sensors (MSS) and the numerous experience in the use of magnetometric equipment.

In the process of carrying out work and research, the employees of the SPL were asked to help equip the existing and temporarily discontinued MO and OP with modern methodological material and magnetometer tools, as well as the development of new DMVS adapted to local conditions of application. As a result of the activities of SPL employees, since 2005, several models of various types and types of modern magnetometers and variation stations have been created at the Institute, information about which can be found in publications [21-23, 26, 30-37].

Figure 6 – General view of various variants and models of the DMVS "Quartz-4" design and one of the device creators V.V. Lyubimov

At the same time, the main attention was paid to the modernization of traditional IZMIRAN devices – DMVS based on QMS. In 2005, the employees of SPL, on the basis of the experience of development of previously created various domestic and foreign DMVS, created a new model of DMVS called "Quartz-4" [22]. This DMVS solution differed from all previously created stations in the new design of PEC, electronic units, compactness and economy. All the main elements of the station are created using modern SMT installation technologies and using SMD components. This basic development of the Quartz-4 DMVS and its subsequent modifications Quartz-4MO, Quartz-4AC and other models (20 sets of various variants and models of DMVS were manufactured) in recent years have been placed in various MO and OP on the territory of the Russian Federation (see Fig. 4).

Fig.6 shows the very first model of the Quartz-4 DMVS (stationary version for MO) and more modern models of the Quartz-4MO and Quartz-4AC DMVS, which are created for scientific and expeditionary research in unattended and rarely serviced OP and for stationary work, including

in the MO. For the area of FN in the period from 2007 to 2011. 4 sets of DMVS "Quartz-4MO" was made [34]. The latest modification of this DMVS called "Quartz-4AC" [30-31] passed comprehensive metrological tests and type tests and, according to their results, in 2016 was included in the State Register of Measuring Instruments (No. 63306-16).

The main technical characteristics of some models created at the Institute of DMVS for their comparison are presented in the Table in the work [38].

Figure 7 – Elements of the MVS schema

It should be noted that in recent years, various creative groups of IZMIRAN employees have created (on the basis of early QMS designs) several other variants of quartz DMVS, some of them are currently installed and working at the MO (see Fig. 4) and OP both in the south of the Russian Federation and in the area of the FN [27, 29, 39]. Some of these developments were prototypes or working mock-ups, so no publications about them (and the necessary technical and operational characteristics for comparison) were found.

In 2006, an employee of IZMIRAN K.Kh. Kanonidi created a three-component digital MVS [24], which passed metrological tests and, according to their results, in 2007 was included in the State Register of Measuring Instruments (No. 35059-07) and is used for special work. Similar digital MVS were installed in ten more OPs on the territory of Russia (in the Crimea and the Caucasus), as well as in the OP at the FN (Karpogory, Arkhangelsk Region), where stationary observations have been conducted for more than a decade at the IZMIRAN scientific polygon [27], and at the MO on Kaliningrad Region. This MVS [24, 27] is a modern digital observational magnetometric device with the ability to transmit measured data over a cellular telephone network. Technical characteristics of the MVS are presented in the Table in the work [38].

Digital and visualizable daily analog data of some from these digital MVS on OP can now be observed in real time on the IZMIRAN geophysical data site: <http://forecast.izmiran.ru/index.php>.

In 2005, a digital station called DMVSB was created in SPL on the basis of QMS designed by V.N. Bobrov with an electrical output. The main technical characteristics of this DMVS are indicated in the work [21]. A distinctive feature of this development was that it had three variants (see Fig.8) of the design of the sensor unit, which were designed to conduct research work – both in the field and in the conditions of MO.

It should be noted that the process of DMVS creating with the use of modern means of engineering and technology, despite the death of the generation of the main ideologists of quartz magnetic instrumentation, continues. Already at present, the Institute has created a number of designs and prototypes of DMVS based on QMS, which develop this theme and have new higher technical and operational characteristics [32, 33, 35-37, 40-43]. At the same time, new opportunities and technologies for data exchange and transmission are used in the developments.

Figure 8 – General view of various variants and models of the DMVSB design

Along with DMVS, IZMIRAN employees in recent years have been actively working on the creation of devices of other types and structures based on QMS and quartz threads. Work in this direction of magnetometric instrumentation was successful, as a result of which a series of various unique devices was created that allow for scientific research and special work, for example, to study the magnetic moment of a part or product or to determine the angles of inclination with high accuracy.

CONCLUSION

The author would like to express his gratitude and appreciation to the scientists and employees of IZMIRAN, participants in the work on the creation of DMVS, authors of unique computer programs for previously created at the institute and for modern DMVS, which are used in many MO. With the help of the software created by them for the DMVS, IZMIRAN devices can be easily integrated into many domestic and foreign projects for the collection, processing and collection of the received digital data.

References:

1. Schelting V.F. Quartz Z-variometer//Tr. NIIZM, L., 1953. Vol.7 (17). S.144-187.

2. Schelting V.F. Field Variational Magnetic Station. USSR Author's Certificate No. 104677. Class 42c, 43. Published 1954.
3. Bobrov V.N., Schelting V.F. All-quartz twisting frame for variometers and magnetometers. USSR Author's Certificate No. 104725. Published in BI No. 22, 1956.
4. Mansurov S.M. Theory of magnetic variational devices // Trudy NIIZM. M., 1957. Vol.12 (22). S.91-182.
5. Bobrov V.N. Universal highly stable sensitive element with zero temperature coefficient for magnetometers, variometers and microvariometers that register any component of the Earth's magnetic field // Trudy IZMIRAN. M., 1961. Vol.18 (28). S.55-67.
6. Geomagnetic devices. Academy of Sciences of the USSR. VDNKh USSR. IZMIRAN Avenue. M., 1961. – 4 p.
7. Bobrov V.N. Serie of quartz magnetic variometers // Geomagnetism and aeronomy. M., 1962. Vol.2, No3. S.348-356.
8. Bobrov V.N. Quartz geomagnetic devices // Vestnik Akademii nauk SSSR. M., 1963. Vol.2. S.82-84.
9. Bobrov V.N. Three-component field magnetovariation station "IZMIRAN-4" // Geomagnetism and aeronomy. M., 1965. Vol. 5, No. 5. C.892-895.
10. Burtsev Yu.A. Development of the theory of quartz static magnetometers and ways to expand their technical capabilities. Diss. for the degree of Cand. techn. Sciences. M.: IZMIRAN, 1970. -134 p.
11. Bobrov V.N. Five-component field electromagnetic variation station // Geomagnetism and aeronomy. M., 1971. Vol.11, No.3. S.570-573.
12. Burtsev Yu.A., Mansurov S.M., Timofeev G.A. Autonomous variation station for geomagnetic research in Antarctica // Geomagnetic instrumentation. M.: Nauka, 1977. S.60-64.
13. Magnetic devices. Prospekt SKB FP AN SSSR. L.: Nauka, 1978.- 5 p.
14. Bobrov V.N., Gaidash S.P., Kulikov N.D. Two-component marine magnetic variation station // Fundamental problems of electromagnetic research in the oceans. M.: IZMIRAN, 1979. S.45-50.
15. Digital magnetic variation station DMVS-2. Prospekt SKB FP. M.: NTO AN SSSR, 1982. – 2 p.
16. Digital magnetic variation station CMVS-6. Prospekt SKB FP AN SSSR, 1987. – 2 p.
17. Zaitsev A.N. Research in the Arctic and Antarctic // Electromagnetic and plasma processes from the Sun to the Core of the Earth. M.: Nauka, 1989. S.315-327.
18. Burtsev Yu.A. Magnetic variation station Quartz-3E in international research // Sbornik «Materialy mezhdunarodnaya shkola-seminara po computernogo avmatizatsiya i informatizatsiya». M.: MGU, 2000. S.89-91.
19. Amiantov A.S., Zaitsev A.N., Odintsov V.I., Petrov V.G. Variations of the Earth's Magnetic Field: Database of Digital Data of Magnetic Observatories of Russia for the Period 1984-2000 (brochure and optical disc CD-ROM). M.: StroyArt, 2001. – 52 p.
20. Highly stable 3-component quartz magnetic variation station "Quartz-3EM". IZMIRAN Avenue. Troitsk, 2004. – 4 p.
21. Bobrov V.N., Lyubimov V.V. Digital magnetovariation station // Sensors and Systems / New devices. M.: «OOO SenSiDAT», 2005. №2. S. 40-42.
22. Burtsev Yu.A., Kiriakov V.Kh., Lyubimov V.V. Digital magnetovariation station «QUARTZ-4» // Sensors and Systems / New devices. M.: «OOO SenSiDat», 2006. №1. S.45-48.
23. Belov B.A., Burtsev Yu.A., Kiriakov V.Kh., Lyubimov V.V. Digital quartz magnetic variation stations // Sensors and Systems / New devices. M.: «OOO SenSiDat», 2006. №5. S.35-38.
24. Three-component digital magnetovariation station MVS. Instruction Manual. Troitsk: IZMIRAN, 2006. – 14 p.
25. Gaidash S.P. Marine electromagnetic research: creation of instrumental and methodological support, experiment, results. Diss. for the degree of Cand. Phys.-Math.. Sciences. M.: IZMIRAN, 2007. -165 p.

26. Kiriakov V.Kh., Lyubimov V.V. New developments: digital magnetic observatory // *Sensors and Systems / Design and production of sensors, devices and systems*. M.: «OOO SenSiDAT», 2010. No.4. S.22-24.
27. Kuznetsov V.D., Kanonidi Kh.D., Kanonidi K.Kh., Ruzhin Yu.Y. Karpogorsky scientific stationary IZMIRAN // *Materials of the international conference "Development of academic science in the homeland of M.V. Lomonosov"*. Arkhangelsk, 2011. S.109-114.
28. Kiriakov V.Kh., Lyubimov V.V. Digital magnetovariation automatic station // *Dynamika naukowych badan – 2012 / Materialy VIII Miedzynarodowej naukowo-praktycznej konferencji 07 – 15 lipca 2012/ Fizyka. Przemysl*, 2012. Vol.22, S.31-35.
29. Kanonidi K.Kh., Kanonidi Kh.D., Petrov V.G. Development of the network of geomagnetic observations IZMIRAN // *Electromagnetic and plasma processes from the bowels of the Sun to the bowels of the Earth*. M.: IZMIRAN, 2015. S.77-87.
30. Lyubimov V.V. Three-component magnetovariation station // *Pribory*. M., 2016. №12. S.1-4. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2567474
31. Lyubimov V.V. New devices for geomagnetic research: magnetovariation station // *Nauka I studia /Fizyka. Przemysl*. 2016. NR 24-6 (160). S.28-33.
32. Lyubimov V.V. Highly stable magnetic measuring converter based on quartz sensors for digital geomagnetic observatories of various latitudes // *Nauka I studia. Przemysl*. 2016. Vol.10. S.400-413.
33. Lyubimov V.V. Digital magnetometer converter based on quartz magnetic sensor and miniature photoelectric converter of linear and angular displacements // *Nauka I studia. Przemysl*. 2016. Vol.11. S.82-94.
34. Lyubimov V.V. To the 45th anniversary of geomagnetic research IZMIRAN in the Far North: The history of the creation and application of digital magnetometers (Obzor) // *Ural scientific bulletin. Physics: Geophysics*. Uralsk: TOO Uralnauchkniga, 2018. Volume 2 No. 8, S.3-14. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.2565661
35. Lyubimov V.V. Magnetic measuring converter for digital variation stations // *Pribory*. M., 2019. №8. PP. 11-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3463661
36. Lyubimov V.V. Two-component quartz variometer // *Eurasian scientific association*. M., 2019. №12 (58). PP. 50-53. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3603859
37. Lyubimov V.V. Quartz variometer // *American Scientific Journal*. Elmhurst AV, Queens, NY, United States. 2019. № (32). Vol.2. Pp.31-35. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3596918
38. Lyubimov V.V. K 80-letiyu IZMIRAN: digital quartz magnetic variation stations (the history of their creation and application) // *Eurasian scientific association*. M., 2020 No.4 (62). pp. 480-493. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3818532
39. Lyubimov V.V. Quartz magnetic field sensors, magnetovariation stations and devices on their basis (Bibliography) // *Eurasian Scientific Association*. M., 2020. No.5 (63). PP.130-144. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.3888083
40. Lyubimov V.V. Quartz magnetovariation stations IZMIRAN at polar observatories and observation points: from analog to digital instruments // *Eurasian Union of Scientists (ESU)*. M., 2021. No.11 (92) Vol. 1. PP. 8-18. DOI: 10.31618/ESU.2413-9335.2021.1.92.1506
41. Lyubimov V.V. Digital variometer-magnetometer-gradientometer with a fixed measuring base based on a quartz magnetometer converter // *Eurasian Scientific Association*. M., 2021. No.12 (82). PP. 92-95. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5833336
42. Lyubimov V.V. Compact digital quartz variometer for observatories and scientific research // *Journal of Engineering and Technology Development Research (JETDR)*. ArtMedia24. Industriestrasse 8,74589 Satteldorf Germany. 2022. Vol.1, No.1. Pp.14-16. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6077888
43. Lyubimov V.V. Quartz magnetometer-gradiometer // *Journal of Engineering and Technology Development Research (JETDR)*. ArtMedia24. Industriestrasse 8,74589 Satteldorf Germany. 2022. Vol.1, No.1. Pp.11-14. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6077729